

The City of Shamballa is a reflection of the Great City of Light

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Past Life profile:

You were male in your last Earthly incarnation.

You were born somewhere around the territory of modern Austria approximately in 1750.

Your profession was dramatist, director, musician, bard.

Your brief psychological profile in that past life:

You were geographically impaired, found it difficult to travel, but had the ability to understand others deeply. You were a great humanitarian and investigator of the human condition. May have been a spiritual leader who traveled in a group and aided others.

Lesson that your last lifetime has brought to the present:

Your lesson - to conquer jealousy and anger in yourself and then in those who will select you as their guide. You should understand that these weaknesses are caused by fear and self-regret. You will incorporate this lesson, find great love and lead many onto the same rewarding path.

Discover your past life here

http://www.links2love.com/horoscope/psychic_my_past_life.htm

Chris Comish

10pt

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Comment

Comments

Esta Lior

• October 15, 2025 at 12:47pm

Reply | Edit | Delete

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Adrian

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Esta Lior

• October 9, 2025 at 11:23am

Chris Comish

Sign Out

azrael-tra...

The unrescued I will rescue.
The unliberated I will liberate.
The uncomforted I will comfort.
Those who have not attained nirvana, I will
cause them to attain nirvana.

As One reaches the Buddhic plane of
Consciousness, Oneness is Experienced

"As a being, standing in the sun, suffused
with its light, and pouring it forth, would
feel no difference between ray and ray, but
would pour forth along one as readily and
easily as along another, so does one on the
buddhic plane feel brotherhood (or
sisterhood) and pours themselves into any one
who needs their help. One sees all beings as
themselves, and feels that all one has is
another's as much as one's: in many cases,
more another's than one's, because their
need is greater, their strength being less."

~ Arthur E. Powell

"I close with an appeal to all who read these
instructions to rally their forces, to renew
their vows of dedication to the service of
humanity, to subordinate their own ideas
and wishes to the group goals, to take their
eyes off themselves and fix them anew upon
the vision, to guard their tongues from idle
speech and criticism, from gossip and
innuendo, and to read and study, so that the
work may go intelligently forward. Let all
students make up their minds in this day of
emergency and of rapid unfolding
opportunity, to sacrifice all they have to the
helping of humanity. Now is the need and
the demand. The urgency of the hour is

Archangel A:
Transmissio
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Form - Steve

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Archangel Az
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day and night in an effort to relieve humanity and to offset those evils and disasters which are immanent in the present situation. I offer to you opportunity, and I tell you that you are needed -- even the very least of you. I assure you that groups of students, working in unison and with deep and unfaltering love for each other, can achieve significant results. That each of you may so work, and that each of you may lose sight of self in realisation of world need, is the earnest prayer and deepest aspiration of your brother, THE TIBETAN." (A Treatise on White Magic, p. 639/40)

~ The Master Djwhal Khul

"Think, not what you want to do, but what you can do that will help someone else; forget about yourself, and consider others. A pupil must be consistently kind, obliging, helpful—not now and then, but all the time." (The Masters and the Path, p. 80)

~ The Master Kuthumi

"Father....Not my will, but yours be done."

~ Luke 22:42

"Be universal love--radiating towards no one object or person in particular but, like the sun, shining on everything in its path." ~ Buddha

"So long as your attitude is open-hearted and accepting and you embrace and take

Chris Comish

Sign Out

Archangel A: Transmissio Dissolving A Attachment Form - Steve Archangel Az Transmissio Dissolving A Attachment Form - Steve Nobel meditation is assist Starsee releasing all attachment to

rez

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Barbara A. Daniels

Frie
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Luminita Muntean

January 9, 2024 at 2:49pm

Hello, thank you for your long lasting activity. I feel blessed to be here with you.

Reply | Edit | Delete

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Chris Comish >

Luminita Muntean

January 15, 2024 at 10:21am

I feel the same. I appreciate you.

Sherry Ste

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Karla Chave z

~ RICHARD RUDD

"All is love and love is all."

~ Richard Rudd

Perfect Attributes of the 7 Rays:

1. Strength.

"I will be strong, brave, persevering in his service."

2. Wisdom.

"I will attain that intuitional wisdom which can be developed only through perfect love."

3. Adaptability or Tact.

"I will try to gain the power of saying and doing just the right thing at the right moment—of meeting each man on his own ground, in order to help him more efficiently."

4. Beauty and Harmony.

"So far as I can, I will bring beauty and harmony into my life and surroundings, that they may be more worthy of him; I will learn to see beauty in all Nature, that so I may serve him better."

5. Science (detailed knowledge).

"I will gain knowledge and accuracy, that I may devote them to his work."

Chris Comish

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Chris Comish

• November 15, 2023 at 12:22pm

Bodhisattva VOW

The unrescued I will rescue. The unliberated I will liberate. The uncomforted I will comfort. Those who have not attained nirvana, I will cause them to attain nirvana.

Reply | Edit | Delete

arashnemati

• June 2, 2023 at 12:00am

Hello, dear teacher. I have a question. I have a patient to whom I am sending energy. There is a lady who has a disordered menstrual cycle and

Hary Om

Frie Foll

DRISS TAZI

Frie Foll

Joshua

Frie Foll

All Friends

○
 I will unfold within myself the mighty power
 of devotion, that
 through it I may bring others to him."

7. Ordered Service.
 "I will so order and arrange my service of
 God along the lines
 which he has prescribed, that I may be able
 fully to take advantage of the
 loving help which his holy Angels are always
 waiting to render."

~ C.W. Leadbeater, The Masters and the Path
 (pp. 259-260)

"The Heart (Love) is the key to leaving the
 matrix of separation and entering the Unity
 of God."

"Do all the good you can, by all the means
 you can, in all the ways you can, in all the
 places you can, at all the times you can, to
 all the people you can, as long as ever you
 can." ~ John Wesley

"No act of kindness, no matter how small, is
 ever wasted." ~ Aesop

"Gratitude is the sign of noble souls." ~
 Aesop

"Trust in the many invisible arms that hold
 each one of you, that carry and comfort you,
 and know that not ever do you walk alone,

Chris Comish
 wanted to get
 advice for her
 treatment.

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Chris Comish >
 arashnemati
 · June 6,
 2023 at
 3:57pm

Greeting
 s. I
 answered
 your
 question
 in a
 message

·
 Namaste

·
[Reply](#) | [Edit](#)
 | [Delete](#)

RichRaelian
 · March 10, 2023
 at 3:38am

Hi Chris!
 I'm not sure
 I deserve
 this honor of
 being the
 member of
 the month
 and I'm
 almost
 speechless
 but there
 was a site
 where I
 enjoyed that
 honor
 unfortunatel
 y I'am not a
 member

manifest a fulfilling life for you – one that is in perfect alignment with the higher plan of your soul and that of Mother Earth – manifest under grace, in perfect, harmonious and miraculous ways. And may this manifest through the abundant sources through which Mother/Father God provide. May all always be well in your world." ~ The Ascended Masters

"There is neither Past nor Future. There is only the Present." ~ Ramana Maharshi

"That which is above is from that which is below, and that which is below is from that which is above, working the miracles of one." ~ Hermes Trismegistus

"Be the I within the I. Be the observer within the doer"

"If I do not go to the hell to help the suffering beings there, who else will go? ... if the hells are not empty I will not become a Buddha. Only when all living beings have been saved, will I attain Bodhi." ~ Kṣitigarbha

Love is the glue of the universe. Through acts of Love we attract our Spirit. May we realize that We are all One.

"You are accepted and loved with open arms. May you be blessed. We are ready to

Chris Comish

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of me my true
goodbye!

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Sirian Starlight

• November 28,
2022 at 5:35pm

You are light who guides many. May your path be strengthened by the presence of love through those whom you are bonded to and share a journey with.

In wisdom, those who are special, will rise to know why they have been respected as such. May many blessings be with you and all ways lead to your abundance in well being.

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Alisha Lewis

• November 13,
2022 at 6:00pm

Chris Comish

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1 2 3 4 5
of 43

The fruit of silence is prayer; the fruit of prayer is faith; the fruit of faith is love; the fruit of love is service; the fruit of service is peace" ~ Mother Teresa

"The sign of a great leader is not one who receives power from others, but one who empowers others. When leadership works, it creates leaders, not followers. True leadership is not about amassing followers, it is about building teams, it is about creating social structures that effect change, however small or great, in the world."

"Be the master and cause of your reality, not the victim of it."

"Tend the fire of your heart- with each act of love the fire grows more toward me."

God (during a message to me during meditation)

"Do good works on Earth."

God (during another message to me)

"If you judge people, you have no time to love them."

~ Mother Teresa

"It's amazing Molly. The love inside, you take it with you."

"No life can express, nor tongue so much as name, what this enflaming, all-consuming love of God is. It is brighter than the sun, it is sweeter than anything called sweet; it is stronger than all strength; it is more nutrimental than food, more cheering to the heart than wine, and more pleasant than all the joy and pleasantness of the world. Whoever obtaineth it is richer than any monarch on earth; and he who getteth it is nobler than any emperor can be, and more potent and absolute than all power and authority."

~ Jakob Böhme

"Wisdom tells me I am nothing. Love tells me I am everything. And between the two my life flows."

~ Nisargadatta Maharaj

"The final goal is to help humanity achieve all seven levels of initiation instead of focusing on your own. In truth, you live as much in your brother and sister as you live in yourself. To help your brother and sister is to help yourself, for your brother and sister are you, since God has only one child. Any time you hold back on giving to your brother and sister due to competition, ego factors, or separation, you are, in truth, just shorting yourself. Your brother and sister are mirrors, and what you receive in this incarnation is exactly what you give- no more and no less. Make the choice never to

are God, whether they have taken any initiations or not."

~ Dr. Joshua David Stone

"I have been all things unholy. If God can work through me, He can work through anyone."

~ St Francis of Assisi

"A human being is part of the whole called by us universe, a part limited in time and space. We experience ourselves, our thoughts and feelings as something separate from the rest. A kind of optical delusion of consciousness. This delusion is a kind of prison for us, restricting us to our personal desires and to affection for a few persons nearest to us. Our task must be to free ourselves from the prison by widening our circle of compassion to embrace all living creatures and the whole of nature in its beauty. The true value of a human being is determined primarily by the measure and the sense in which they have obtained liberation from the self. We shall require a substantially new manner of thinking if humanity is to survive."

~ Albert Einstein

"When the power of love overcomes the love

"Be universal in your love. You will see the universe to be the picture of your own being."

~ Sri Chinmoy Ghose

"When you chase the light, darkness cannot catch you."

"For where there is reverence for good works and light in the mind, even darkness fleeth away from him."

~ The Testament of Benjamin, from the Apocrypha

"The secret of health for both mind and body is not to mourn for the past, nor to worry about the future, but to live the present moment wisely and earnestly."

~ Buddha

"Always be nice to people on the way up; because you'll meet the same people on the way down."

~ Wilson Mizner

"Become a conscious observer and practice detachment. Do not allow yourself to be pulled into a vortex of negative energy created by others. Learn to stand firm and in control, as the director of your sacred energy. Do not allow anyone to disturb your serenity and harmonious nature."

"Jesus said, "There was a rich man who had much money. He said, 'I shall put my money to use so that I may sow, reap, plant, and fill my storehouse with produce, with the result that I shall lack nothing. Such were his intentions, but that same night he died. Let him who has ears hear."

~ The Gospel of Thomas, from the
Apocrypha

"Do not hold grain waiting for higher prices when people are hungry."

~ Zoroaster, also known as Zarathustra

"Jesus said, "If your leaders say to you, 'Behold, the kingdom is in the sky,' then the birds in the sky will get there before you. If they say to you, 'It is in the sea,' then the fish will get there before you. Rather, the kingdom is inside you and outside you. When you know yourselves, then you will be known, and will understand that you are children of the living Father. But if you do not know yourselves, then you live in poverty, and embody poverty."

~ The Gospel of Thomas, from the
Apocrypha

"Be good, be kind, be humane, and charitable; love your fellows; console the afflicted; pardon those who have done you wrong."

~ Zoroaster, also known as Zarathustra

~ Hafiz

"May God comfort you and your family in
this time of sorrow."

~ Words to say to someone who has lost a
loved one

"Father, forgive them for they know not what
they do."

-Jesus, from Luke 23:34

"As you sow, so shall you reap"

"When the Nazis came for the communists, I
remained silent; I was not a communist.
When they locked up the social democrats, I
remained silent; I was not a social democrat.
When they came for the trade unionists, I
did not speak out; I was not a trade unionist.
When they came for the Jews, I remained
silent; I was not a Jew. When they came for
me, there was no one left to speak out."

~ Pastor Martin Niemöller (1892–1984)

"Ego is always LOVE'S opposite. Love raises
vibration and ego lowers it. Ego is a mental
essence that each of us is made to endure
for as long as we walk the planet. Ego is that
thing that tells us in our mind, "No you can't
do that ... because you're not talented, thin,
good-looking, wealthy, intelligent, young,
strong, interesting or intuitive ENOUGH!"
This is the voice of the Liar. The Liar is the
voice of ego. Let me put it this way:

sure ego is not far behind. Ego wants to keep you earthbound and Heavenless for as long as it can. It is an essence that has been sent here to learn just as you have. However, it has a duty to challenge each of us and cause us to learn as it learns for itself. There is nothing to fear about the ego. It is just a fragile, spoiled child that screams and rants until it gets what it wants. And like any child, if you ignore it during its temper flare long enough, sooner or later it will get the message that those kinds of methods are not productive and will not yield positive results. If you understand the ego, you will understand the concept of the devil. Satanic frequency is the LOW-RANGE frequency that surrounds us in our collective thinking. It is the opposite of the HIGH, INCOMPREHENSIBLE LOVING frequency of God. Please hear me out on something...be careful of the music you listen to, the movies or TV you watch, the gossip or negative speaking you participate in. All these things LOWER the Soul's vibration. Lower vibration brings depression, disillusionment, disease and despair. The lower our Soul's vibration falls, the more these dark things come upon us. Once you fall into LOWER vibration, immediately seek to amend it with LOVING, HIGHER VIBRATIONAL THOUGHT. It is like anything else, the more you put into something, that is what the end result will be."

~ Christian Andreason

" For the Light is with me, and I myself am with the Light."

~ Pistis Sophia, A sacred Gnostic text

Chris Comish

Sign Out

self, so you can radiate love to all.”
~ Chris Comish

LOVE IS THE TRUTH

LOVE IS THE WAY

AND LOVE IS THE LIFE

NO ONE COMES UNTO GOD UNLESS THEY
KNOW HOW TO LOVE

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